

The great voices that are not heard: Narrative on the situation regarding the rights of children and adolescents in Ecuador.

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INTRODUCTION

A few years ago in many countries a very famous phrase was said that is "the young people are the future of the country", but this applied to our times and realities, is a bit wrong, because "young people are the present of the country", a phrase that is beginning to be used very frequently, to reflect that the true entities of change are they, and although it sounds very ironic our future as generations of ancestors depends a lot on the decisions made by the young now.

The research work is named The great voices that are not heard: Analysis of the situation regarding the rights of children and adolescents in Ecuador, because I will emphasize two situations: First, the children's voice, girls and adolescents in Ecuador, are not taken into account, which caused a ignorance of the reality of this social sector. Second, the situation of the rights of children and adolescents in Ecuador, instead of improving, stalled by different factors such as: lack of information, bad public policies, and bad administrations, etc.

According to the Social Observatory of Ecuador (2018) "nine of the seventeen Objectives of Sustainable Development (OSD), and twenty-seven of the one hundred and sixty-nine goals are directly related to the rights of children and adolescents". This concatenated with the information compiled by Riera (n.d.), which tells us that:

From the Convention on the Rights of the Child, approved in 1989, signed by Ecuador in 1990, the rights of girls, boys have been gaining importance; in addition, the Constitution prioritizes the integral development of children and adolescents and ensures the full exercise of their rights, to which it grants primacy over others (...) this means that the entire society as a whole must care for and protect all girls, boys and adolescents.

Developing

The mandates of the Convention on the Rights of the Child, signed by Ecuador in 1989, and the Constitution of the Republic of Ecuador (2008), in its article 45, validates the universal character of these rights that, "supposedly, do not only apply to each and every one of the boys, and the girls, but in turn deserve special attention to those who present social disadvantages and face greater difficulties in exercising them". (Social Observatory of Ecuador, 2018).

The web portal Humanium (nd), refers to Ecuador as one of the countries that "most progress has been made in improving the situation of children, however, there are still large cultural gaps, especially in relation to education, health and in general living conditions of children". But this information can be partially true, or a little outdated given that, the big problem for what is happening in the country is that we

do not know for sure what the statistics look like today, this based on what the journalist Pandzic (2021) informs us, who affirms that "...Today's analyzes and decisions are made based on a demographic composition and socioeconomic data dating back to 2010, the year in which the last population census was made...", this may be, because as the journalist Pandzic mentions (2021), "the pandemic has been disruptive for the entire social fabric, which has forced the government to use outdated information becoming irrelevant for purposes of build a development plan that seeks to attend the needs of the country". But this problem is not only from Ecuador, as Abramo (2017) clarifies, stating that "Latin America continues to be the most unequal region in the world, despite significant progress made by countries during the first decade and a half of the 21st century". Inequalities in Ecuadorian child poverty are easily identified in the study conducted by the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) (2005), reflecting that:

There are ethnic differences in child poverty, children belonging to indigenous households register a percentage of 59%, with 42% are Afrodescendants, and mestizos present 25%, these children suffer deprivation of material resources, spiritual and emotional needs to survive, develop and prosper, which prevents them from enjoying their rights, reaching their full potential or participating as full and equal members of society.

But the same UNICEF (2005), tells us that "it is important to stand out that the high indicated percentages are lower than that of 2006".

For its part, the Geneva-based Committee on the Rights of the Child recommends to the Ecuadorian government implement public policies to reverse these figures. It is worth clarifying that, "poverty is a political problem, and eradicating it is a moral imperative, (...) this is the challenge for Ecuador and the world..." National Secretariat of Planning and Development (SENPLADES), (2017, p. 13). Similarly, "the lack of policies specifically targeting school-age children, and the absence of state programs aimed at adolescents is part of the urgent actions to improve the situation". (Humanium, nd). Because boys and girls are inserting in a "previously constructed social context, which is often one of poverty and inequality" UNICEF (2005).

The government should equitably allocate resources to eliminate "multidimensional poverty in early childhood and child malnutrition, to achieve an integral protection of children and measures to deal with violence against these" Social Observatory of Ecuador (2018).

In the study carried out by the Children's Rights portal (2021), it reflects that in Ecuador:

One in ten children works to be able to help his family financially, since the minimum age for work was set at 15 years, (...) many children work in dangerous and deplorable conditions, (...) some work in garbage dumps, banana plantations or in the mining sector, running serious risks to their health and their lives.

Although poverty has decreased both for the total population and for children and adolescents, “since 2014, it shows a stagnation, in addition to the gap of poverty among the general population and children has not changed substantially in these recent years” Social Observatory of Ecuador (2018). As reported by statistics in 2004, “14% of boys and girls between the ages of 5 and 17 only work, and did not go to school or simply did not work or go to school” Humanium (n.d.). In a story narrated by a low-income girl tells us that “this year it was my turn to work and leave school. I will return the following year and my brother will have to work” International Plan Ecuador (2013).

It is socially understood that “poverty drastically limits the opportunity that children have to prosper, mostly in matters related to education, housing and healthcare” Children’s Rights (2021). This is a very alarming situation, given that “250,000 children do not attend school and one in three does not do it because he dedicates his time to working activities, or cannot do it because of his economic conditions” Dávalos (2019). Creating at the same time “a barrier in their social development, since they do not have enough time to study and work at the same time” Children’s Rights (2021).

To deal with this, we must achieve the OSD 1: End Poverty, in the case of childhood. For this, it is necessary to “deepen what are the groups of boys and girls who are at a greater disadvantage, because they suffer the impact of geographic and ethnic inequalities, based on how many and where the children of the country are” Social Observatory of Ecuador (2018). But how is it from knowledge for all there is a lack of an accessible, verifiable and real information system offered by the National Institute of Statistics and Census (NISC).

The three fundamental pillars of a country that are the State, society and the family, must ensure as a priority the comprehensive development of girls and boys, to thus promote the exercise of their rights in a warm, familiar and safe environment for the reason that , as is known by many, the problems that already existed have been aggravated by the COVID-19 pandemic.

In the country there are efforts to guarantee the rights of children and adolescents; for example, projects and strategies focused on the protection of rights and eradication of violence against girls, boys and adolescents, however, there is still much to be done, the inter-institutional work of the State of law must be strengthened to guarantee more girls,

boys and adolescents the enjoyment of their rights to guarantee a dignified life and integral development. (Riera Borja, undated)

However, it must be remembered that, in the current context, there is still a lot of work to be carried out, for which the reality of the territory for children must be taken into account, in urban and rural contexts.

Conclusions

The three fundamental pillars of a country: state, society and family, must build a country that protects, guarantees and fulfills the rights of all boys, girls and adolescents, given that significant inequalities still exist, as is the case of poverty limiting children's opportunities to thrive, we should not leave all the work to the state, since the state is inefficient on its own. We must leave of being conformist paternalists, and begin to be the change, which we need not only for us, but for all, children and adolescents, creating spaces in which they feel heard and protected, in order to later get empowered by the word, and be the entities of change that we need at this time.

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